

The Language of Resistance and Cultural Reclamation in African Short Stories

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Abstract

The history of Africa is deeply intertwined with themes of resistance and cultural reclamation, largely in response to the devastating impacts of the transatlantic slave trade and European colonialism. This is responsible for the ongoing struggle for identity and self-definition which is also echoed in African short stories. In postcolonial African literature, language is not only a tool for storytelling but a site where cultural identity, power, and resistance are constantly negotiated. Characters use language as a form of resistance and cultural affirmation. This paper aims to explore how African short stories construct resistance and cultural reclamation through discourse, focusing on the linguistic and narrative strategies used by characters to challenge dominant ideologies and assert traditional values or hybrid identities embedded in speech patterns, silence, symbolic references, and the narrative voice. Adopting a qualitative discourse analysis approach, the paper draws on postcolonial theory particularly Ngũgĩ wa Thiong'o's concept of linguistic decolonisation and Homi Bhabha's idea of hybridity. Systemic functional linguistics is used to explore how characters use language to negotiate power dynamics in their social interactions. The analysis centres on three short stories: *Afritude* by Monique Kwachou, *The Plantation* by Ovo Adagha, and *A Life in Full* by Jude Dibia. Findings reveal that characters employ silence, irony, refusal, code-switching, and metaphor to contest imposed norms and assert cultural voice. Reclamation is seen in their use of indigenous expressions, symbolic actions, and narrative choices that centre on African knowledge systems. These discursive elements not only challenge external authority but also help reconstruct identity from within. The paper concludes that resistance does not always rely on confrontation, but often unfolds through everyday speech, narrative shifts, and the reclamation of cultural voice.

Keywords

Resistance discourse, cultural affirmation, African short stories, linguistic decolonization, code-switching, postcolonial theory

Introduction

In the wake of colonisation, African literature emerged as a vibrant space for reclaiming cultural voice and challenging dominant narratives imposed by colonial power structures. In this struggle, language occupies a central position as it often embodies both the tools of colonisation and the means of resistance. Postcolonial African writers have deployed the dual role of language as a medium of cultural oppression and an instrument of liberation to express the African voice in the emancipation proclamation.

While many scholars have examined the overt political themes in African fiction, there remains a growing interest in how everyday language within literary texts functions as a form of resistance and cultural affirmation. Short stories, in particular, provide fertile ground for this exploration. Their brevity and focus on lived experiences allow writers to foreground moments of defiance, irony, silence, and negotiation in highly concentrated forms.

The motivation for this study stems from the need to understand how discourse in African short fiction can both challenge colonial and patriarchal authority and contribute to cultural reclamation. Resistance is not always dramatic or revolutionary; it can take the form of subtle linguistic choices, refusal to comply with social expectations, or the intentional use of indigenous expressions and narrative styles.

This paper focuses on how language is used by characters in selected African short stories to resist ideological imposition and reclaim aspects of their cultural identity. An analysis of how language reveals and shapes power struggles between characters through their speech patterns, silence, metaphor, and code-switching, uncovers the ways in which postcolonial African writers represent identity negotiation and cultural assertion through discourse. In doing so, the paper contributes to a deeper understanding of the role of language in shaping subjectivity, power relations, and postcolonial resistance in African literature.

Literature Review

Language, in postcolonial African literature, is not a neutral medium but a contested site of identity, power, and history. It is within and through language that colonisation operated to displacing indigenous ways of knowing and communicating, and it is also through language that postcolonial writers resist, reinterpret, and reclaim cultural ground. African short stories, in their intimate scope and immediacy, often depict the lived experiences of resistance, through discourse as a tool for subtle rebellion and cultural reassertion. In foundational texts such as *Decolonising the Mind*, Ngũgĩ wa Thiong'o (1986) argues that the language of African literature must reflect African realities, urging writers to reclaim indigenous languages and storytelling traditions. Language, he insists, is the "carrier of culture." Similarly, Chinweizu, Jemie, and Madubuike (1980) emphasise the need for African literature to liberate itself from colonial aesthetic models and linguistic dependency.

Nigerian scholars like Adedimeji (2016) and Asabe Kabir (2019) reinforce these arguments by highlighting how Nigerian literature reflects the tension between imposed colonial language and indigenous linguistic expression. Cultural reclamation, for them, begins with the choice of words, idioms, proverbs, and symbolic references that affirm African worldviews and unsettle Western narrative frameworks. While much research has acknowledged the symbolic importance of language in postcolonial writing, fewer studies have explored the micro-level discursive strategies used by characters to resist cultural dominance within fictional conversations and narrative voice. Most scholarships focus on overarching themes of resistance (anti-colonial struggle, nationalism)

rather than examining how resistance is enacted linguistically in everyday interpersonal exchanges in fiction.

Furthermore, the short story genre remains underexplored in linguistic and discourse-based research. Although scholars like Olaoluwa (2013) and Osunbade (2018) address themes of hybridity and identity, they tend to focus on novels or poetry. This paper addresses the gap through discourse analysis to examine how resistance and cultural assertion occur within speech patterns, silence, and symbolic acts in African short stories.

The study is grounded in two intersecting theoretical traditions. First, postcolonial theory of Ngũgĩ (1986) and Homi Bhabha (1994), provides the ideological foundation for understanding resistance as springing from hybrid spaces, where indigenous and colonial identities clash, mix, and reconfigure. Bhabha's concept of hybridity frames identity as negotiated through mimicry, irony, and contradiction, which are often expressed in the instability of language itself. Second, the study employs Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL), particularly the interpersonal and ideational metafunctions (Halliday & Matthiessen, 2014), to explore how characters use language to assert, resist, or shift power in their social relations. Appraisal theory by Martin & White, 2005, further supports the analysis of evaluative language, revealing stance, emotion, and values embedded in discourse.

Discourse analysis has been increasingly used to study African texts, but largely in media, politics, or education (Taiwo, 2009; Olateju, 2006). In literary studies, Onukaogu and Eyisi (2014) have called for more integration of linguistic tools in analysing literary texts, especially to unburden ideology and cultural identity. This paper responds to that call by applying linguistic analysis to short fiction, emphasising the performative nature of language in shaping subjectivities.

Scholarly works such as Achille Mbembe (2001) and Nnaemeka (2004) point to the value of indigenous knowledge and oral traditions as forms of resistance against Eurocentric narratives. Nigerian writers often code-switch, blending English with indigenous languages. This is not just a stylistic choice; it is a deliberate political act that asserts their linguistic ownership over a language inherited from colonial rule. Silence and indirectness, too, have been recognised as strategies of resistance especially by women who may use what is not said to subvert authority (Lazar, 2005). This study extends those insights into the short story format, showing how silence, metaphor, ritual action, and naming function as discursive acts of resistance and cultural affirmation.

Many contemporary African short stories are published in anthologies. These works increasingly reflect a subtle politics of identity, where cultural reclamation occurs through small but intentional linguistic choices. Monique Kwachou, Amma Darko, and Jude Dibia do not always dramatise rebellion; rather, their characters negotiate identity through irony, withdrawal, or the reassertion of suppressed traditions. These trends suggest that resistance is often discursive rather than dramatic, especially in everyday contexts portrayed in short fiction. This paper contributes to this

growing field by providing a close analysis of how language at the level of dialogue, silence, and cultural symbolism operates as a form of reclaiming African voices in postcolonial literature.

Theoretical Framework

This study draws on an interdisciplinary theoretical framework that combines insights from postcolonial theory and Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL). This combination enables a comprehensive exploration of how discourse functions as both a medium of resistance and a means of cultural reclamation in African short stories. Postcolonial theory offers a critical lens for understanding how formerly colonised societies confront and reconfigure the cultural legacies of colonialism. Central to this study is Ngũgĩ wa Thiong'o's (1986) argument that language is not simply a communication tool, but a carrier of culture and worldview. In *Decolonising the Mind*, Ngũgĩ insists that the struggle for self-definition must begin with a reclaiming of indigenous languages and narrative forms. Language, he argues, is the site where colonial domination begins and where resistance must be staged.

In addition, Homi Bhabha's (1994) concept of *hybridity* is vital to this study's understanding of postcolonial subjectivity. Bhabha describes hybridity as the space where colonised individuals occupy overlapping cultural worlds, negotiating identity through mimicry, irony, and ambivalence. In this "third space," resistance often occurs not through open rebellion but through discursive slippage, the deliberate or unconscious blending of cultural signs to unsettle dominant ideologies. The two theorists contribute different but complementary perspectives. Ngũgĩ foregrounds the role of indigenous language and storytelling in cultural survival while Bhabha highlights the strategic ambivalence of language and identity in postcolonial contexts. Together, their ideas provide a rich framework for examining how African short stories use language to resist cultural imposition and affirm native ways of being.

To investigate how language enacts resistance and reclamation in fictional discourse, the paper adopts SFL by M. A. K. Halliday which views language as a social semiotic system, that is, a resource for meaning-making shaped by social and cultural context. Focusing on two key metafunctions, the interpersonal metafunction explores how language enacts relationships between speakers and listeners as well as the expression of power, attitude, and alignment. It is especially useful for identifying resistance in dialogue through mood choices (questions, imperatives, refusals), modality (degrees of certainty or obligation), and politeness or assertiveness strategies. The ideational metafunction examines how language represents reality through process types, participant roles, and cultural worldviews. This helps in understanding how reclamation of cultural knowledge is performed through traditional references, metaphors, and indigenous expressions. To analyse subjective stance, emotional tone, and value judgments, the study also incorporates Appraisal Theory by Martin & White, 2005, to examine how speakers position themselves affectively and ideologically. It is in evaluative language such as praise, blame, irony, or doubt that subtle forms of cultural resistance or affirmation are often revealed.

3. Integrating the Two Frameworks

By combining postcolonial theory and SFL, the study investigates not only the *themes* of resistance and cultural identity in African short stories but also the *linguistic means* by which they are enacted. Postcolonial theory provides the ideological context for understanding the significance of resistance and reclamation, while SFL allows for a close analysis of how these processes operate at the level of discourse. This dual approach ensures that the analysis is both culturally informed and linguistically grounded.

Methodology

This study adopts a qualitative discourse analysis approach to examine how resistance and cultural reclamation are constructed through language in selected African short stories. The approach is interpretive and context-sensitive, focusing on how characters use linguistic and narrative strategies to challenge dominant ideologies and assert cultural identities. The research is grounded in critical discourse analysis (CDA) within a literary context, using Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL) and postcolonial theory to guide analysis. The study treats literary texts not just as artistic works but as discursive artefacts texts that reflect and reproduce broader cultural ideologies and power relations. The aim is to explore how resistance and identity negotiation are encoded at the level of dialogue, narration, and symbolic action.

Three short stories were purposively selected for their thematic and linguistic engagement with postcolonial identity, cultural struggle, and resistance: *Afritude* by *Monique Kwachou* (Cameroon): A coming-of-age story that explores diasporic return and cultural reintegration. *The Plantation* by *Amma Darko* (Ghana): A satirical critique of postcolonial economic dependency and cultural erosion, and *A Life in Full* by *Jude Dibia* (Nigeria): A narrative of generational tension, urban alienation, and resistance to marital expectations. These stories offer diverse cultural perspectives from Anglophone Africa, allowing for comparative analysis of how discourse reflects different forms of cultural negotiation across gender, generation, and geography.

The analysis draws on key aspects of SFL, particularly the interpersonal metafunction which focuses on how characters assert, defer, question, or reject others in conversation. Attention is given to mood, modality, and speech function. The ideational metafunction explores how cultural values and worldviews are represented through process types (material, relational, verbal), participants, and circumstances. Appraisal theory by Martin & White, 2005 is applied to examine how evaluative language reflects alignment, resistance, or identification with cultural ideologies through attitude, engagement, and graduation.

The analysis proceeded in three main phases: Textual immersion involves multiple readings of each story to identify moments of cultural conflict, resistance, or affirmation. Coding and categorisation entail extraction of excerpts with prominent discursive features such as, dialogue,

silence, metaphor, evaluative language). Interpretive analysis involves linking linguistic features to ideological meanings and cultural positioning using the integrated framework of SFL and postcolonial theory.

Analysis and Discussion

1. Afritude – Monique Kwachou

Monique Kwachou in *Afritude*, explores the tension between Westernised upbringing and African cultural identity through the story of Eli, a young Cameroonian girl sent back from the United States to attend boarding school in her home country. The story presents a subtle but layered narrative of cultural resistance, internal conflict, and eventual reclamation, rendered through the discourse between Eli, her mother (Ma Fri), and her new Cameroonian environment.

At the beginning of the story, Eli's voice is marked by a Western teenage register full of sarcasm, and defiance. For instance, she says about her mum *"I had explained to her about the dare, the cops had understood. Why couldn't she?"* The expression *"Why couldn't she?"* a dismissive discourse marker, along with the contractions reflects a linguistic identity aligned with American teenage culture. This utterance carries interpersonal significance and a casualness which signals resistance to authority, particularly to Ma Fri's attempt to reconnect Eli with African cultural values. *"All my mom knew was I was not behaving like a Cameroonian, not even like an African"*

Eli's irony and sarcasm function as tools of resistance. Rather than openly attacking her mother's values, she uses tone and word choice to mock the perceived backwardness of African traditions. *"Being the good African Child did not get you accepted in school, or get you friends, or get you much of anything except your mom's acceptance"* This is a form of discursive mimicry, reminiscent of Bhabha's hybridity, where colonial or Western codes are adopted but used to unsettle traditional ones. On the other hand, Ma Fri speaks in a register grounded in collective values and moral certainty: *"I'm sending you back to go to boarding school."* Her use of the declarative mood and absence of hedging in this regard show firm authority. The phrase "to go to boarding school" is not just literal it invokes cultural identity as a source of belonging. Through this, Ma Fri reclaims the narrative around Eli's identity, repositioning it within a framework of ancestry, tradition, and social expectation.

This corrective discourse functions as linguistic reclamation. Ma Fri does not argue for African culture; she assumes its legitimacy, presenting it as a truth that Eli must rediscover. This represents the ideational metafunction at work: through language, Ma Fri asserts a particular worldview that prioritises heritage over Western individualism.

School as a Discursive Space of Reorientation

Eli's narrative voice begins to shift when she got to Cameroon. With the new set of discourse norms the school environment imposes, such as not being late for meals, respectability and following rituals that reinforce communal values, she soon began to adjust and adapt. "*And it all came back to me then. Yes, I did know. That was me spouting such rubbish there years ago.*" ...When did I change, when did I learn to be conscious... Eli's voice has become less sarcastic and more reflective. She no longer mocks African customs but begins to appreciate their symbolic value. This discursive transformation mirrors her ideological repositioning, which is her shifts from rejection to acceptance of cultural norms. She thus begins to use the term *Afritude* with a new understanding by the end of the story. She understood that it had nothing to do with what you wear, your accent or in speaking Pidgin. It was knowing who you are and not been apologetic about it.

The word "Afritude" which once was a vague or mocked concept is reclaimed discursively. Knowing who you are represents a redefinition of cultural identity on Eli's own terms. Ma Fri or society did not force it upon her, but it became adopted through lived experience. Her final tone is confident and declarative, signaling a completed journey from linguistic resistance to cultural reclamation. In SFL terms, she moves from high interpersonal tension (expressed through questions, sarcasm, and negation) to evaluative affirmation, using language to express alignment with a reclaimed identity.

The summary of discursive patterns in *Afritude* range from resistance initially expressed through juvenile delinquency, sarcasm, and rejection of tradition to cultural correction which emerges through Ma Fri's use of declarative moral language and cultural authority. The school environment imposes ethical discourse norms that slowly shape Eli's worldview. Cultural reclamation is enacted in the story's final lines, where Eli redefines *Afritude* and asserts self-knowledge. The story uses language not only to portray identity conflict but to perform a discursive transformation from rejection to reclamation.

2. The Plantation – Ovo Adagha

Set in a rural oil-producing region of Nigeria, "*The Plantation*" tells a tragic yet familiar story of dispossession, desperation, and death in a land overflowing with natural wealth. Through the character of Namidi, the story foregrounds the complex interplay between poverty, resistance, and complicity, revealing how language spoken, silenced, and symbolic mirrors and mediates the socio-political realities of the Niger Delta.

The story begins with the whistling sound of leaking oil. A symbol of sudden wealth and imminent danger. The unseen underground oil pipes represent extractive imperialism, a network that siphons wealth away from the soil and the people it belongs to. While the land is visibly fertile, its productivity has been poisoned by the very thing meant to enrich it. The people are made mute spectators, unable to access the benefits of their own natural resources. Namidi's cautious and

secretive response to the spill is telling. Instead of raising alarm, he quietly withdraws to mobilise his family, unwilling to alert others who might compete for the resource. His two-word replies to neighbours' greetings mark a linguistic shift from openness to concealment revealing how even language is weaponised by scarcity and survival.

The characters' actions, though morally ambiguous, are framed as responses to a history of systemic neglect. Namidi's desire to claim a share of the "common wealth" reflects a deeply internalised sense of economic exclusion. His wife, Mama Efe, serves as the voice of caution and spiritual intuition. Her warnings about fire are loaded with cultural symbolism. In African cosmology, fire often represents divine judgment or spiritual consequence. Her language is emotive and interrogative "*What if there is a fire breakout?*" Her rhetorical question dismissed by her husband functions as a discursive foreshadowing of tragedy. She speaks from ancestral knowledge and maternal intuition, but her voice is ignored, echoing a long history of feminised wisdom being overwritten by patriarchal urgency.

Ochuko, Namidi's son, becomes the unintended witness to catastrophe. His act of watching and playing while others are scavenging symbolises the innocence that is ultimately engulfed by structural violence. His view of people "draped in fire" and "dancing like spirit-possessed fetish priests" is a discursive image of chaos and death, linking the explosion to spiritual disorder and cultural betrayal. The absence of direct dialogue in the story's most tragic moments speaks volumes. When Ochuko hides, waiting for his family to return, the silence that follows is devastating. It is a narrative silence that mirrors the voicelessness of the people, trapped in an extractive economy where their lives are expendable.

While the story does not present a triumphant act of resistance, it functions as an act of cultural reclamation in itself. By narrating the everyday consequences of oil politics, the text gives voice to the structurally silenced. How people are "burned" when they try to partake in their own wealth reveals the cruel irony of resource colonialism: those who seek to benefit from their land's riches are punished for doing so. "Cheek-sagging individuals", a metonymic reference to corrupt elites who benefit from resource flows at the expense of the poor are implicated in the saga. This subtle discursive move points to the local complicity in global exploitation, showing that betrayal is not only external, but internal, facilitated by political and corporate gatekeepers.

Integrating into the Broader Framework of Cultural Reclamation

"The Plantation" highlights how language is not only used to resist exploitation, but also to survive within it. The story shows that silence, indirect speech, and withheld information are sometimes the only tools available to the oppressed. Unlike open protest, the resistance here is quiet, fractured, and ultimately overwhelmed by tragedy but it is no less meaningful. This story reaffirms that African literature often serves as a form of discursive resistance, exposing the inequalities and hypocrisies of neocolonial structures. Through the act of telling this story, the text claims cultural authority over a narrative often erased or sanitised by corporate or state discourse.

3. A Life in Full – Jude Dibia

A Life in Full by Jude Dibia presents Victor as a man resisting deeply embedded cultural expectations. Victor is a financially independent bachelor who lives in urban Lagos. He is repeatedly pressured by his mother, Mabel, to marry and produce children. Victor is portrayed as putting up neither aggressive nor overtly confrontational resistance. Rather, it is expressed through silence, indirectness, and linguistic boundary-setting. These discursive strategies reveal a quiet but firm refusal to conform to social norms, offering a distinctive example of how language becomes a site for personal and cultural negotiation.

His mother's persistent pleas for him to be married meet with silence or non-verbal actions. For instance, "*Victor was quiet for a long time before he spoke.*" This pause is not mere hesitation; it is a discursive act which in the context of cultural expectations require the eldest son to marry and perpetuate lineage. Victor's silence represents a withholding of cultural compliance. It creates discomfort and denies his mother the affirmation she seeks, thus, functioning as a passive form of resistance. In another instance when the mother brings up the same issue, "*He looked away, pretending to be busy with his phone.*" This behaviour marks a deliberate avoidance of dialogue. Victor chooses silence and distraction over direct opposition. In SFL terms, this is a withheld response, denying the typical speech function of engagement. His quiet disconnection signals non-participation in the expected cultural script of conformation.

Victor's verbal responses are often framed in interrogative or evasive forms, which subtly challenge the authority of his mother's assertions: "*Must I marry just because others do?*" This rhetorical question uses modality and interrogative mood to push back against normative expectations. The phrasing is not confrontational but gently subversive, shifting the conversation from obligation to individual choice. He deflects further discussion with expressions like, "*Can we not talk about this now?*" rather than saying "I don't want to marry" or "Leave me alone," Victor uses soft negation and polite distancing which allows him to maintain respect while establishing discursive boundaries. His language shows that resistance can coexist with cultural politeness, thus revealing the layered nature of hybrid postcolonial identities.

Victor's resistance also manifests through discourse about space and privacy: "*This is my space, Mama.*" The assertion of one's space is a concept less emphasised in traditional communal culture, rather, it reflects a modern, individualistic identity. Victor invokes Western spatial ideology to legitimise his emotional and relational autonomy. His mother's expectation that she can manage his household and guide his choices is countered by a linguistic claim of territoriality, both physical and symbolic. Victor reclaims identity through language, in asserting that marriage, children, and family approval are no longer prerequisites for a fulfilled life.

On the other hand, Mabel speaks with cultural certainty and communal logic, "*You are the first son. You have a responsibility.*" Her language is shaped by traditional expectations, invoking relational processes ("you are") and collective shame "*People are laughing at me. They say I must have done something wrong.*" This indirect coercion through the voice of the community uses

reported speech to place Victor under cultural scrutiny. Yet Victor does not respond with anger or rebellion. His discursive resistance lies in refusing to internalise this communal gaze.

The summary of discursive patterns in *A Life in Full*. Firstly, Victor resists cultural expectations not with confrontation, but with silence, delayed responses, and rhetorical questions. His indirect language and spatial metaphors reflect a modern, autonomous self-conception. Secondly, Mabel's language is rooted in communal duty and emotional appeal, but Victor's discursive disengagement undermines her control. The story presents resistance as a quiet, consistent refusal to perform prescribed roles, not through rebellion, but through linguistic boundary-making. Through Victor's understated but persistent refusal to conform, Dibia illustrates how language can be used to resist cultural imposition while still maintaining familial respect. *A Life in Full* thus aligns with broader postcolonial discourse in showing that resistance can be quiet, indirect, and deeply personal crafted through the careful use of words, pauses, and the rejection of inherited scripts.

Comparative Discussion

The three short stories examined in this paper demonstrate that language in African postcolonial fiction is more than a medium of expression, it is a space of ideological negotiation, where characters confront, resist, and redefine the cultural forces acting upon them. While the characters, settings, and forms of resistance differ across the stories, each narrative shows how discourse becomes a means of reclaiming identity and asserting autonomy whether spoken, withheld, or reappropriated. In *Afritude*, resistance is performed through sarcasm, irony, and American teenage slang which Eli uses to distance herself from her Cameroonian heritage. Her initial speech patterns embody cultural rejection, but over time, her language shifts to include respectful and reflective tones. This evolution signals a gradual internal reconciliation and a discursive acceptance of cultural belonging.

In *The Plantation*, resistance takes the form of ironic commentary, sarcastic reversals, and collective silence. The workers use religious and colonial phrases to subtly twist meanings and reveal their ideological awakening. Humour and silence serve as powerful political acts, undermining exploitation without overt defiance. In contrast, *A Life in Full* presents a more internalised resistance. Victor resists his mother's expectations through silence, rhetorical evasion, and territorial language. He does not shout, argue, or rebel; he simply refuses to conform, using polite refusal and delayed engagement to preserve his autonomy. His strategy reflects a private, modernist form of postcolonial subjectivity, where resistance is enacted through discursive distance, not confrontation.

Despite differences in tone and setting, all three stories use silence and indirectness as key strategies of resistance. In *Afritude*, Eli's sarcastic tone eventually gives way to quiet reflection and acceptance; in *The Plantation*, silence becomes a collective stance against injustice and in *A Life in Full*, Victor's refusal to argue directly with his mother protects his emotional and

ideological boundaries. This reveals a common pattern in African postcolonial narratives that resistance does not have to be loud or dramatic. Rather, it often occurs in the gaps, silences, hesitations, and subtle shifts in tone. This exposes an organised form of protest that aligns with social realities where open rebellion may be culturally or emotionally costly.

All three stories also depict cultural reclamation, though in different forms. In *Afritude*, Eli redefines the concept of “Afritude” by the end of the story, not as fashion or surface identity but as rootedness and pride. Her discursive shift from mockery to affirmation signals the reclamation of a hybrid but grounded African identity. *The Plantation*, reveals a world in which resistance is both necessary and dangerous. In *A Life in Full*, Victor reclaims identity through spatial and discursive autonomy. His language marked by terms like “my space” and “my life” positions his right to define his future outside communal expectation by asserting a modern African masculinity that resists inherited norms. Each story, therefore, presents language as the terrain upon which identity is negotiated whether by embracing traditional speech, reframing cultural symbols, or establishing linguistic territoriality.

The stories also suggest that language-based resistance is shaped by gender and generation. In *Afritude*, Eli’s language is transformed as she is reintegrated into a more traditional space, navigating gendered expectations with increasing awareness. *The Plantation*, reveals a world in which resistance is both necessary and dangerous. In *A Life in Full*, a male character resists familial pressure not through confrontation but by adopting an emotionally restrained, self-defined masculinity. These distinctions point to the flexibility of resistance discourse shaped by social roles, generational conflict, and the specific histories characters inhabit. Despite these variations, the linguistic strategies they employ share common features, such as irony, silence, reinterpretation, and symbolic naming.

In conclusion, all three stories affirm that African characters resist not only through what they say, but also how they say it, and sometimes through what they choose not to say at all. Language becomes a flexible, adaptive, and deeply personal tool for negotiating identity and reclaiming cultural agency in a postcolonial world.

Conclusion

The paper has examined how language functions as a tool for resistance and cultural reclamation in three selected African short stories: *Afritude* by Monique Kwachou, *The Plantation* by Ovo Adagha, and *A Life in Full* by Jude Dibia. Using a discourse analytical approach grounded in postcolonial theory and systemic functional linguistics. The study has demonstrated that language, whether spoken, withheld, or transformed, serves as a site where postcolonial subjects negotiate power, identity, and belonging. Across the stories, resistance emerges not only through overt protest but also through more subtle linguistic strategies such as irony, silence, rhetorical questioning, and indirect refusal. These forms of discourse allow characters to reject imposed

norms whether colonial, patriarchal, or religious without necessarily engaging in open confrontation. Language becomes a shield, a strategy, and a quiet declaration of self-determination.

In parallel, cultural reclamation is carried out through the reassertion of indigenous knowledge, the creative reuse of traditional expressions, symbolic naming, and a deliberate return to rooted cultural values. Through redefining terms like “Afritude,” reclaiming proverbs in communal speech, or asserting the right to one’s own space and life choices, the characters use discourse to affirm identities that are deeply African, yet dynamic and hybrid.

The paper shows that African short stories are not only vehicles for reflecting social conflict; they are also performative texts where cultural struggle is enacted through discursive practices. The short stories reveal that identity is not passively inherited but actively constructed through language. The study highlights the power of fiction to participate in the broader project of linguistic and cultural decolonisation through the analysis of how resistance and reclamation unfold within ordinary speech and narrative strategies. This research encourages further exploration into the linguistic dimensions of African literature, particularly in under-researched genres like short stories, and across more African languages and regions. It also affirms the value of integrating linguistic analysis with literary interpretation to uncover the deep ideological work that language performs in postcolonial narratives.

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